

Evaluating model performance for spatial assessments of wildfire ignition risk

Contribution to Deliverable 2.5a: 'Estimate impacts on assets (condition, functions)'

for the Project D5-2 Climate Change Impacts on Natural Capital

March 2026

Summary

This report is a product of the Scottish Government Strategic Research Programme project JHI-D5-2 'Climate Change Impacts on Natural Capital' and contributes to Deliverable D2.5a: 'Estimate impacts on assets (condition, functions)' (due December 2026).

The purpose of this report is to evaluate the performance of the Machine Learning (ML) model produced by Gagkas et al. (2025) for spatial assessments of ignition risk by conducting a validation exercise based on a set of 70 independent historical fires (i.e., burnt areas not used to train the ML model) for the 2020 - 2025 period. The ML model simulates the ignition probability for a given date and location as the function of fire weather and potential presence of an ignition source and by considering land cover (fuel), soil and terrain information. This approach differs to the fire weather-driven Fire Danger assessments produced by the Scottish Wildfire Forum; hence, to avoid any unintended confusion, here we use the term 'Ignition Risk' instead of 'Fire Danger' used previously for the ML model outputs (Gagkas et al., 2025).

The need for increased capabilities to understand fire danger and ignition risks has been highlighted following publication of other reports from the JHI-D5-2 'Climate Change Impacts on Natural Capital'. These show how much Scotland's climate has already changed and what the future climatic conditions influencing fire danger and risk may be:

- [Climate Trends and Future Projections in Scotland](#)
- [Climate Extremes in Scotland](#)
- [Assessment of Natural Capital exposure to current and future meteorological drought](#)
- [Fire danger assessment of Scottish habitat types](#)
- [Spatial assessments of future wildfire danger in Scotland](#)

Advances in Technical Capabilities

This report has been developed through technical advances made in the JHI-D5-2 project related to new analytical capability for conducting spatial ignition risk assessments, and generation of scripts for extraction of historical weather datasets and visualisation and plotting of the simulation results.

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Introduction

The purpose of this work was to use an independent validation approach to evaluate the performance of the Machine Learning (ML) model for conducting spatial assessments of wildfire ignition risk. We used weather forecasts from historical simulations provided by the ERA5 reanalysis (Hersbach et al., 2023) for the initial fire dates (i.e., dates of fire detection) of 70 historical wildfires that occurred in Scotland in the 2020 - 2025 period to simulate wildfire ignition probabilities and map respective ignition risk classes within the areas burnt by these fires. Burn areas were obtained from the European Forest Fire Information Service (EFFIS¹) and have been delineated using analysis of satellite imagery (mainly Sentinel-2).

As described in Gagkas et al. (2025), burnt areas detected and delineated from remote sensing are used because there is no systematic recording of ignition locations for the wildfires that have occurred in Scotland. Hence, the spatial ignition risk assessment for these historic fires covers both ignition locations and areas of fire propagation and spread. It was not expected that all of the burnt areas used in this exercise had a high ignition risk at the time of fire initiation; during wildfire spread, sustained combustion generates a progressively intensifying radiant and convective heat flux that drives moisture loss, pyrolysis, and thermal degradation in adjacent fuels, enabling vegetation that was initially too wet to ignite to reach ignition temperature and transition to flaming combustion. This process explains why areas of initial low ignition risk can be burnt as the fire builds-up. Hence, since the actual ignition locations are unknown to us, the focus of the validation exercise was not to investigate whether the model identified all burnt areas as of High ignition risk but rather whether the model identified enough Moderate to High ignition risk locations and areas, with fuels dry enough to ignite, that justify fire initiation and spread. It is important to note that the ML ignition risk assessment does not then extend to fire behaviour modelling, as this requires a different modelling approach. Improving ignition risk assessment can be seen as an essential first step in developing an overall improvement in wildfire risk assessment.

Methods

Overview

The validation exercise was conducted using the following steps:

- Collation of EFFIS burnt area polygons in Scotland for the 2020 - 2025 period with sizes ≥ 100 ha ($n=70$). We used the 100 ha threshold to ensure that only wildfires were selected and not smaller prescribed burns that can also be detected by EFFIS due to the high spatial resolution of the imagery used (Gagkas et al., 2023). These fire polygons were appropriate for use in the independent validation because they were not used in training the ML model, which used fire polygons from the 2013 - 2019 period.
- Extraction of required spatial covariate layers (Table 1) within the areas of the selected fire polygons. Land cover was determined by aggregating the Land Cover of Scotland (LCS) 1988 (MLURI, 1993) classes to main fuel categories of Broadleaves; Conifers; SeminatURAL grasslands; Heather; Bogs; and Montane vegetation. We used the National Forest Inventory Scotland 2023²

¹ [EFFIS - Welcome to EFFIS](#)

² [National Forest Inventory Scotland 2023 | Forestry Commission Open Data website](#)

to update forest and woodland information in the LCS map. Spatial covariates were harmonised to a 50m grid cell resolution.

- Extraction of fire weather indices calculated from weather forecasts for the specific dates of fire initiation from the historical simulations provided by the ERA5 reanalysis dataset; these were combined with the spatial covariates to build the input dataset.
- ML model run using the input dataset to produce ignition probabilities (1%-100%) for each 50m pixel covering the burnt areas of the selected fires, and group probabilities into ignition risk classes: Very Low (VL): 0% – 15%; Low (L): 15%-45%; Moderate (M): 45%-55%; High (H): 55%-85%; Very High (VH): >85% .
- Production of maps showing ignition risk classes for the areas covered by the 70 fire polygons, calculate coverages by risk classes and explore patterns and relationships.

Fire polygons

Figure 1 gives the locations and burnt area sizes of the 70 fires for the 2020 - 2025 period that were used in this validation exercise, Figure 2 gives the land cover (fuel) composition of fire polygons aggregated by Region, and Table A1 in the Appendix gives basic attributes (Local Authority, fire date and burnt area size) and land cover (fuel) composition for each fire polygon. The total burnt area of all fire polygons was 41,222 ha.

Almost 60% of this area (23,750 ha) was burnt in 2025, when Scotland experienced its most severe wildfire season (Scottish Government, 2026), including the largest wildfire ever recorded in the United Kingdom around Carrbridge and Dava Moor (included in this study, see Tables A1 and A2: Fire_ID: 273772). Selected fires that occurred in 2023 and 2022 accounted for a further 15% (6,351 ha) and 11% (4,550 ha), respectively, of the total burnt areas, while less than 4,500 ha were burnt in the fires in each of 2020, 2021 and 2024. Half (50%) of the total area was burnt in April, followed by 25% being burnt in June and 15% in May. It is worth noting that of the 10,477 ha burnt in the fires that occurred in June, 9,809 ha belonged to one single fire (Carrbridge and Dava Moor fire), and the remaining area was burnt in 3 fire incidents (burnt areas 132 - 283 ha).

Heather was the dominant land cover (fuel) category within the selected fire polygons, accounting for 64% (26,220 ha) of the total burnt area, followed by Bogs with a further 26% (10,916 ha). There were 2,069 ha of Seminalural Grassland burnt within the fire polygons, and 817 ha of montane vegetation, while Broadleaves and Conifers accounted for 1% (408 ha) and 2% (791 ha), respectively, of total burnt area. Most of the burnt areas of Heather and Bogs were in fire polygons located in the North and West regions, most of the Conifers burnt were in fire polygons in the Central region, while most of Seminalural Grasslands burnt were in fire polygons in the South region (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Locations and burnt area sizes (in ha) of the 70 fires for the 2020 - 2025 period used in the validation exercise. Labels show Regions (see Table 1 for description). © Crown copyright and database right (2026). All rights reserved. The James Hutton Institute, Ordnance Survey Licence Number AC0000812928.

Figure 2. Areas (in ha) of land cover (fuel) categories within the burnt areas of the 70 fires for the 2020 - 2025 period used in the validation exercise, aggregated by Region.

Historical Fire Weather Forecasts

In the absence of fire weather codes specific to Scottish climatic and vegetation conditions (Gagkas et al., 2025), the ML model uses fire weather indices of the Canadian Fire Weather Index System (CFWIS) (Figure 3, Table 1). A detailed description of the CFWIS indices is given in Taylor et al. (2021). In brief, CFWIS-based fire weather is used in the ML model as a proxy of the moisture of different fuel fraction types (FFMC, DMC, and DC), the effect of wind (ISI), while FWI is used as a proxy for overall fire danger, mainly for forest fires.

Weather variables for the initial dates of the selected fires were derived from the ERA5 reanalysis dataset (Hersbach et al., 2023) provided by the Copernicus Data Store. ERA5 is the fifth generation European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) reanalysis for the global climate and weather for the past 8 decades and provides historical reconstruction of meteorological conditions from 1940 onwards. Reanalysis combines model data with observations from across the world into a globally complete and consistent dataset using the laws of physics. This principle, called data assimilation, is based on the method used by numerical weather prediction centres, where every so many hours (12 hours at ECMWF) a previous forecast is combined with newly available observations in an optimal way to produce a new best estimate of the state of the atmosphere,

called analysis, from which an updated, improved forecast is issued. Reanalysis works in the same way, but at reduced resolution to allow for the provision of a dataset spanning back several decades. Reanalysis does not have the constraint of issuing timely forecasts, so there is more time to collect observations, and when going further back in time, to allow for the ingestion of improved versions of the original observations, which all benefit the quality of the reanalysis product.

For this study, daily noon (12:00 UTC) climate variables (2m temperature, relative humidity, 10m wind speed, and precipitation) were extracted from ERA5 reanalysis ($0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ spatial resolution) at each fire event location for the relevant time periods, then processed through the Canadian Forest Fire Weather Index System using the `cffdrs` R package (Wang et al., 2017) to derive the required fire danger indices (FFMC, DMC, DC, ISI, and FWI).

ERA5's $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ spatial resolution equates in Scotland to a 28 km (Latitude) x 15 km (Longitude) grid. This resulted in all fire polygons being covered by single grid squares, and hence only one set of weather and fire weather index values was used to simulate ignition risk at each individual fire polygon.

Figure 3. Components of the Canadian Fire Weather Index system (CFWIS) (from Taylor et al., 2021)

Model simulations

The weather and fire weather index values for the initial fire dates were integrated in the input dataset with the spatial covariates (Table 1), which was inputted to the ML model (in R, `ranger` package) to generate ignition probabilities for these dates and within the fire polygons at a 50m grid cell resolution.

As described in Gagkas et al. (2015), the formulation of ignition risk classes (previously termed fire danger classes) using the predicted probabilities was informed by the model predictions for both the training and independent samples, which showed that most misclassifications (false negatives and false positives) occurred for predicted probabilities between 0.45 to 0.55, while true positives and true negatives in most times had prediction probabilities >0.60 and <0.40 , respectively. Hence, the following ignition risk classes were defined:

- Very Low (VL): ≤ 0.15 probability.
- Low (L): $> 0.15 - \leq 0.45$ probability.
- Moderate (M): $> 0.45 - \leq 0.55$ probability.
- High (H): $> 0.55 - \leq 0.85$ probability.
- Very High (VH): > 0.85 probability.

Table 1. Description of collated covariates for developing the training dataset for the fire danger model.

Code	Description	Type	Source	Reference
TEMP	Daily temperature (°C) at fire date	Continuous	Historic ERA5 Reanalysis	Hersbach et al., (2023)
PREC	Precipitation total (mm) at fire date	Continuous		
FFMC	Fine Fuel Moisture Code at fire date	Continuous		
ISI	Initial Spread Index at fire date	Continuous		
DMC	Duff Moisture Code at fire date	Continuous		
DC	Drought Code at fire date	Continuous		
FWI	Fire Weather Index	Continuous		
Elev	Elevation above sea level (in metres)	Continuous	Ordnance Survey digital elevation model at 50m grid resolution (OS DTM 50) provided by OS Data Hub	-
Slope	Slope (in radians)	Continuous		Zevenbergen and Thorne (1987)
LCS	Land Cover of Scotland 1988	Categorical	Natural Asset Register	MLURI (1993)
	National Forestry Inventory for Scotland 2023	Categorical	Forestry Commission Open Data website	-
HOST	Hydrology of Soil Types classification	Categorical	Disaggregated soil series map at 50m grid resolution translated to HOST classes	Gagkas and Lilly (2024)
Season	Assigned based on date of fire initiation	Categorical	EFFIS Burnt Areas	-
UR8	Scottish Government Urban Rural Classification (2022)	Categorical	Geography products - National Records of Scotland (NRS)	OGL
Regions	Aggregated river basins	Categorical	-	Gagkas and Lilly (2019)

Results

Spatial Assessments of Ignition Risk

Simulated wildfire ignition probabilities in each of the 70 fire polygons were used to calculate the areas (Figure 4) and the respective proportions (in %) (Table A2 in the Appendix) assigned to the ignition risk classes. Overall, ~40% of the total burnt area within the 70 fire polygons was assigned to the High ignition risk class, and a further 1% in the Very High ignition risk class. A further ~30% of the

total burnt area was assigned to the Moderate ignition risk class, with the remaining ~30% and 3% of the total area assigned to the Low and Very Low ignition risk classes, respectively.

Based on model simulations, of the 70 fire polygons used in this study, 55 fire polygons had at least 1% and 52 fire polygons had at least 5% of their area being assigned to a High and Very High ignition risk class. In 6 of the remaining 15 fire polygons with no predicted area at High risk, at least 15% of their area was predicted to be at Moderate risk. Ignition risk was High or Very High in 50% or more of the burnt area in 42 fire polygons that covered a total of 17,240 ha, and in 100% of the burnt area in 9 fire polygons that covered 2,615 ha.

Risk was Moderate in 50% or more of the burnt area in 9 of the 70 fire polygons that covered a total of 11,770 ha, and in 100% of the burnt area in 2 fire polygons that covered 407 ha. Risk was Very Low or Low in 50% or more of the burnt area in 17 of the 70 fire polygons that covered a total of 10,651 ha, and in 100% of the burnt area in 9 fire polygons that covered 329 ha.

Overall, 45% and 40% of the area covered by Heather and Bogs, respectively, in the 70 fire polygons was assigned a High ignition risk, with a further 23% for Heather and 42% for Bogs assigned a Moderate ignition risk (Figure 5). Conversely, 78%, 95%, 87% and 87% of the burnt areas that were covered by Broadleaves, Conifers, Seminaturnal Grassland and Montane vegetation, respectively, were assigned a Very Low or Low ignition risk.

Regarding the drivers of predicted ignition probabilities and respective ignition risk, in the 42 fires with 50% or more of their burnt area predicted to be in High ignition risk, median values of FFMC were high and ranged from 83 to 85 for all land covers (fuels). An FFMC of 80 has been suggested as a sensible threshold for moss and litter layer ignition in winter-spring fires in heather moorlands in Scotland (Davies et al., 2013). Median DMC and DC values ranged from 6 to 7 and 16 to 17, respectively, for all fuels, median ISI was ~ 2.5, indicating relatively windy conditions, and median FWI was relatively low, ranging from 1 to 2. Median elevation was below 150m for all land covers, apart from Montane vegetation which was at 450m, and more than 70% of the overall burnt area was in Very Remote Areas (based on the Urban Rural Classification) in the West of Scotland.

Conversely, in the 17 fire polygons where 50% or more of their burnt area was predicted to be in Low or Very Low ignition risk, median values of FFMC ranged from 80 to 82 for all land covers (fuels). In 5 of these 17 fire polygons, FFMC ranged from just 47 to 71; these are quite low values that indicate relatively high to high fuel moisture contents for moss and litter layers in heather moorlands and low potential for ignition. Median DMC and DC values ranged from 1 to 3 and 2 to 12, respectively, for all fuels, median ISI was ~ 0.5, indicating low wind conditions, and median FWI was low, ranging from 0.1 to 0.3. Median elevation was below 110m for all land covers, apart from Montane vegetation which was at 335m, and ~ 80% of the overall burnt area was in Very Remote Areas in Central and Southern Scotland.

Figure 4. Areas (in ha) of each burnt area polygon assigned to Ignition Risk Classes based on simulated fire ignition probabilities for fires that occurred in a) 2020; b) 2021; c) 2022; d) 2023; e) 2024; and f) 2025.

Figure 5. Proportions of burnt areas assigned to Ignition Risk Classes based on simulated fire ignition probabilities, aggregated by Land Cover (Fuel) category.

Maps of ignition risk classes for the 70 fire polygons are given in the Appendix (A3). Here we provide an example of how to interpret these risk maps for a given fire incident, and how they can be used to understand drivers of ignition risk predictions at a given location. For this purpose, we use the Carrbridge and Dava Moor wildfire, the UK’s largest ever recorded wildfire that was formed by the merger of two independently ignited fires at Dava and Carrbridge, northern Scotland, and between June 28th and July 1st 2025 burned nearly 10,000 ha (9,809 ha according to EFFIS), making it the UK’s first megafire under a common size-threshold definition (Pelegrini et al., 2025).

Figure 6 shows the spatial assessment of ignition risk for the area that was eventually burnt by the Carrbridge and Dava Moor. This assessment indicates that if the ML model had been used to predict the wildfire ignition probabilities in the affected area prior to the fire date using weather forecasts similar to the ones provided by the ERA5 reanalysis dataset, then the model would have predicted that 13%, 63% and 24% of the fire polygon area would have been at High, Moderate and Low ignition risk, respectively, and that the ignition probability would have been $\geq 50\%$ in 34% of the eventually burnt area.

Almost all burnt area was covered by Heather moorland (~55%) and Bogs (~43%); 9% and 18% of the Heather moorland and Bog areas were predicted to be at High ignition risk, and 61% and 68% at Moderate ignition risk, respectively. Conversely, 88% to 100% of the remaining small area covered

by other land cover categories (Broadleaves, Conifers, Seminaturnal grasslands and Montane) was predicted to be of Low ignition risk.

Due to the coarse spatial resolution of the ERA5 dataset, the same fire weather indices values for the initial fire date (28/06/2025) were applied for the whole of the fire polygon area. FFMC was relatively high (79.12) but slightly lower than the threshold of 80, DMC was relatively low (4.49) but DC was relatively high (121.1). High DC has been previously found, during warmer and drier than long-term average conditions, to relate to low fuel moisture content in deep organic soil layers in the Cairngorms, Scotland, and to risk of subsurface smouldering combustion (Davies et al., 2013). Moreover, during ML model training and testing (Gagkas et al., 2025), DC, which is calculated using a 52-day time lag, has emerged as an important driver of ignition risk in the summer to autumn months, especially for Heather moorland, Bog and Conifer fires; this indicates that it can be useful for fire weather predictions in prolonged warmer and drier conditions. ISI was also high (3.82), indicating prevalent windy conditions, and finally FWI was also relatively high for Scottish conditions (3.65), but still lower than the indicative threshold of 5, above which forest fire danger seems to become greater (Taylor et al., 2011).

All area (1,226 ha) predicted to be at High ignition risk within the burnt area of the Carrbridge and Dava Moor fire was located on Upland blanket peat (HOST class 29), with 458 ha covered by Heather and 768 ha by Bogs. Probabilities within this High ignition risk area ranged from 56% to 61%. Moreover, 67% of the 6,176 ha predicted to be at Moderate ignition risk were located on Upland blanket peat as well, and 28% on HOST class 15 soils (mainly Peaty podzols). Finally, 58% of the area predicted to have been at High ignition risk belonged to the Remote Rural category of the Urban-Rural Classification) and 42% belonged to the Very Remote Rural category, while 68% of the area predicted to have been at Low risk belonged to the Very Remote Rural category and 32% in the Remote Rural category, indicating that in general ignition risk was predicted to be higher in the, still remote, but more accessible areas within the fire polygon.

Recent analysis by Pellegrini et al. (2025) indicates that the Carrbridge and Dava Moor wildfire occurred under very dry climate conditions. Soil moisture observations by the Soil Moisture Active Passive (SMAP) satellite showed that Scotland was experiencing unusually dry soil moisture conditions preceding the fire. At the time and location of the fire, soil moisture was 1.9 standard deviations below the decadal average for that month in that location. The low soil moisture at the time of the fire is consistent with dry conditions throughout 2025 following a relatively dry 2024 - 2025 winter (precipitation was also very low). Ignition risk predictions agree with the findings of this analysis and demonstrate that the ML model was successful in detecting the relationship between DC and low soil moisture in organic soils, which seems to have been the driver for increasing ignition risk in exposed peat soils within the area.

Figure 6. Map of Ignition Risk Classes at 50 grid cell resolution based on simulated fire ignition probabilities for the burnt area of the Carrbridge and Dava Moor fire.

Conclusions

The main conclusions from this validation exercise are listed below:

- Using historical weather forecasts for the date of fire initiation, the ML-model predicted areas of High ignition risk and/or Moderate ignition risk in 61 of the 70 fire polygons used in this study. In the remaining 9 fire polygons with all their area predicted to have been at Low and/or Very low ignition risk, values of fire weather indices used were low or relatively low, indicating unfavourable conditions for ignition, which was reflected in the model predictions.
- These findings indicate that the ML-model can provide reliable short-term forecasts of Ignition Risk in seminatural areas of Scotland. However, the accuracy of these forecasts greatly depends on the accuracy of the weather forecast predictions and of the land cover (fuel) map used as inputs to the model.
- Moreover, most of historical fire data (2013 - 2019) used to train the ML model were late winter to spring fires in which ignition risk was driven by cold, dry and windy weather conditions. More recent fires included in the validation dataset, especially for 2025, relate to different fire weather conditions: prolonged warm and dry conditions that could have led to low soil and fuel moisture contents. Future climate projections indicate that Scotland will experience further warming over the coming decades, as well as seasonal and spatial shifts in precipitation distribution, with large areas in spring and summer seasons experiencing a potential decrease in meteorological water (evapotranspiration > precipitation), meaning that areas could experience a deficit in the future that could increase the risk of drier soils and vegetation (Rivington and Jabloun, 2023).
- In this context, although the ML-model managed to identify high ignition risk in the 2025 fires, which demonstrates its utility in diverse fire weather conditions, it might be advantageous to re-train the ML model by utilising these more recent fires to better capture emerging fire weather conditions due to climate change.

Next Steps

- Develop a simple visualisation web App that uses freely available weather forecasts to map ignition risk within the Cairngorms National Park. The purpose of this app would be to demonstrate how these modelling approaches can be used to develop early warning systems. Share the app with relevant stakeholders (RESAS, Park's Authority etc.) to get feedback on App utility.
- Depending on availability, collate cloud-free Sentinel-2 satellite imagery for the fires included in the validation prior and during fire initiation to: a) detect locations or areas of ignition and compare with generated ignition probabilities to get a better insight of ML model performance; b) calculate vegetation indices that relate to fuel moisture content and compare burnt vs un-burnt areas to get an insight of asset condition and potential resilience or vulnerability to the threat of fire.

References

- Davies, G.M., Gray, A., Rein, G., Legg, C.J. (2013). Peat consumption and carbon loss due to smouldering wildfire in a temperate peatland. *Forest Ecology and Management*, 308, 169-177. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2013.07.051>
- Gagkas, Z., Lilly, A. (2019). Downscaling soil hydrological mapping used to predict catchment hydrological response with random forests. *Geoderma*, 341, 216-235. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2019.01.048>
- Gagkas Z., Rivington M., Glendell, M., Gimona, A., Martino, S. (2023). Fire danger assessment of Scottish habitat types. Deliverable 2.3b for the Project D5-2 Climate Change Impacts on Natural Capital. The James Hutton Institute, Aberdeen. Scotland. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.7703171>
- Gagkas, Z., Lilly, A. (2024). Spatial disaggregation of a legacy soil map to support digital soil and land evaluation assessments in Scotland. *Geoderma Regional*, 38, Art. E00833. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geodrs.2024.e00833>
- Gagkas Z., Jabloun, M., Glendell, M., Rivington, M., (2025). Development of a modelling approach for conducting spatial assessments of future wildfire danger in Scotland. Deliverable 2.4b for the Project D5-2: Climate Change Impacts on Natural Capital. The James Hutton Institute, Aberdeen. Scotland. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.15794365>
- Hersbach, H., Bell, B., Berrisford, P., Biavati, G., Horányi, A., Muñoz Sabater, J., Nicolas, J., Peubey, C., Radu, R., Rozum, I., Schepers, D., Simmons, A., Soci, C., Dee, D., Thépaut, J.-N. (2023). ERA5 hourly data on single levels from 1940 to present. Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS), DOI: [10.24381/cds.adbb2d47](https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.adbb2d47) (Accessed October 2025)
- MLURI (1993). *The Land Cover of Scotland 1988*. The Macaulay Land Use Research Institute, Aberdeen. ISBN 0 7084 0538 X.
- Pellegrini, A., Schoenecker, J., Baur, M., Kohli, J., Baker, S., Jones, M., Vervebeke, S., Konings, A. (2025). Unprecedented Scottish megafire leads to widespread peat carbon losses. PREPRINT (Version 1) available at Research Square. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-7761772/v1>
- Rivington, M., Jabloun, M. (2023). Climate Trends and Future Projections in Scotland. Deliverable D2.1a for the Project D5-2 Climate Change Impacts on Natural Capital. The James Hutton Institute, Aberdeen. Scotland. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7657945>
- Scottish Government, 2026. Strategic Action Plan on Wildfires. ISBN: 978-1-80643-898-3 (web only) Published by The Scottish Government, March 2026. [Strategic Action Plan on Wildfires](https://www.scottishgovernment.gov.uk/strategic-action-plan-on-wildfires)
- Taylor, A.F.S., Bruce, M., Britton, A.J., Owen, I., Gagkas, Z., Pohle, I., Fielding, D., Hadden, R. (2021). Fire Danger Rating System (FDRS) Report, pp. 1–185. <https://www.scottishfiredangerratingsystem.co.uk/sites/www.scottishfiredangerratingsystem.co.uk/files/SFDRS-Research-Report-Final-15-2-2022.pdf>
- Wang, X., Wotton, B.M., Cantin, A.S. Parisien, M-A., Anderson, K., Moore, B., Flannigan, M.D. (2017). cffdrs: an R package for the Canadian Forest Fire Danger Rating System. *Ecological Processes* 6, 5. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13717-017-0070-z>
- Zevenbergen, L.W., Thorne, C.R. (1987). Quantitative analysis of land surface topography. *Earth Surf. Process. Landf.* 12 (1), 47–56. <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.3290120107>

Appendix

A1. Attributes of the 70 historic fires for the 2020 - 2025 period used in the validation exercise and respective land cover (fuel) composition (in %).

A2. Attributes of the 70 historic fires for the 2020 - 2025 period used in the validation exercise and respective coverages (in %) of the predicted ignition risk classes.

A3. Maps of ignition risk classes for the 70 historic fires for the 2020 - 2025 period used in the validation exercise.

A1. Attributes of the 70 historic fires for the 2020 - 2025 period used in the validation exercise and respective land cover (fuel) composition (in %)

Fire_ID	Local Authority	Fire date	Area (ha)	Broad leaves	Conifers	Semi grass	Heather moor	Bog	Montane
613	Highland	20/04/2020	253	4	1	0	86	9	0
24802	West Dunbartonshire	20/04/2020	112	0	0	36	64	0	0
24398	Dumfries and Galloway	24/04/2020	1571	0	4	7	56	33	0
26155	Highland	04/05/2020	379	0	11	0	80	9	0
26154	South Ayrshire	11/05/2020	182	0	3	0	36	61	0
45967	Eilean Siar	10/02/2021	255	0	0	0	0	100	0
45968	Highland	10/02/2021	272	0	0	3	97	0	0
46319	Eilean Siar	11/02/2021	165	0	0	0	100	0	0
46320	Eilean Siar	11/02/2021	262	0	0	0	80	0	20
46321	Highland	13/02/2021	104	0	0	3	0	97	0
48591	Argyll and Bute	02/04/2021	132	0	0	15	85	0	0
48594	Argyll and Bute	08/04/2021	246	0	0	0	100	0	0
48839	Highland	15/04/2021	111	0	0	0	33	67	0
48775	Highland	16/04/2021	100	0	0	0	94	6	0
48866	Highland	21/04/2021	139	0	0	0	100	0	0
49673	Dumfries and Galloway	02/06/2021	253	0	1	0	67	21	12
192586	Highland	20/03/2022	221	0	0	0	88	12	0
199907	Eilean Siar	20/03/2022	448	0	0	0	91	9	0
199908	Eilean Siar	20/03/2022	220	0	0	0	26	74	0
200124	Highland	22/03/2022	395	6	0	3	53	38	0
200435	Highland	22/03/2022	116	0	0	0	100	0	0
199858	Highland	23/03/2022	330	0	0	0	78	17	5
199973	Highland	23/03/2022	198	0	0	0	0	100	0
200438	Highland	23/03/2022	134	0	0	0	88	1	11
199910	Eilean Siar	26/03/2022	1123	0	0	0	13	87	0
192587	Highland	27/03/2022	187	0	0	0	100	0	0
199855	Highland	28/03/2022	161	0	0	0	100	0	0
200723	Highland	28/03/2022	229	0	0	0	91	8	0
200241	Argyll and Bute	23/04/2022	204	1	1	13	85	0	0
201528	Highland	27/04/2022	584	2	1	0	97	0	0
215691	Perthshire and Kinross	10/03/2023	138	0	0	2	91	7	0
215722	Highland	08/04/2023	450	0	0	0	31	69	0
215724	Highland	08/04/2023	256	0	0	0	88	12	0
215745	Highland	19/04/2023	3448	4	0	2	93	1	0
216024	Highland	20/04/2023	106	1	0	0	91	8	0
216191	Highland	21/04/2023	114	1	0	4	95	0	0
216250	Stirling	22/04/2023	372	1	0	12	10	77	0

D5-2 Climate Change Impacts on Natural Capital. Deliverable 2.5a: Estimate impacts on assets

Fire_ID	Local Authority	Fire date	Area (ha)	Broad leaves	Conifers	Semi grass	Heather moor	Bog	Montane
216217	Highland	05/05/2023	101	0	0	13	87	0	0
216417	Highland	29/05/2023	951	4	4	0	78	14	0
216596	Stirling	06/06/2023	283	0	0	1	21	78	0
216597	Highland	10/06/2023	132	1	45	3	51	0	0
224477	Highland	28/01/2024	499	1	0	3	86	10	0
226639	Highland	09/03/2024	442	0	0	16	31	50	3
226679	Highland	10/03/2024	203	1	0	0	99	0	0
229482	Eilean Siar	01/04/2024	151	0	0	0	15	85	0
228778	Eilean Siar	02/04/2024	199	0	0	0	24	76	0
229804	Highland	24/04/2024	104	12	0	57	29	0	2
230017	Highland	04/05/2024	437	1	0	0	99	0	0
266008	Dumfries and Galloway	19/03/2025	103	0	0	1	75	24	0
265880	Highland	20/03/2025	199	0	0	0	68	32	0
267875	Highland	20/03/2025	313	8	0	10	83	0	0
265848	Highland	21/03/2025	108	0	0	0	25	0	75
265874	Highland	21/03/2025	374	0	0	0	95	4	0
265879	Highland	21/03/2025	498	0	0	1	97	2	0
265896	Highland	21/03/2025	117	0	0	0	92	4	4
267457	South Lanarkshire	01/04/2025	133	0	0	0	90	10	0
265898	Highland	02/04/2025	206	0	0	0	86	0	14
265707	Dumfries and Galloway	04/04/2025	6720	0	5	18	57	14	6
265729	Highland	05/04/2025	136	0	0	21	56	23	0
265761	Highland	06/04/2025	477	0	0	0	75	24	1
267478	Argyll and Bute	06/04/2025	617	2	1	8	86	3	0
267471	North Ayrshire	07/04/2025	157	0	0	0	0	100	0
267111	Highland	08/04/2025	291	0	0	4	4	93	0
267476	North Ayrshire	08/04/2025	889	3	0	17	80	0	0
267110	Eilean Siar	10/04/2025	254	0	0	0	0	100	0
267477	North Ayrshire	10/04/2025	528	0	2	4	47	25	22
267469	North Lanarkshire	11/04/2025	348	0	43	1	8	48	0
267480	Highland	11/04/2025	1080	9	0	0	88	2	0
269798	Highland	22/04/2025	393	1	0	0	99	0	0
273772	Highland	28/06/2025	9809	0	1	0	55	43	0

A2. Attributes of the 70 historic fires for the 2020 - 2025 period used in the validation exercise and respective coverages (in %) of the predicted ignition risk classes

Fire_ID	Local Authority	Fire Date	Area (ha)	VL (%)	L (%)	M (%)	H (%)	VH (%)
613	Highland	20/04/2020	253	1	4	55	40	0
24802	West Dunbartonshire	20/04/2020	112	8	77	15	0	0
24398	Dumfries and Galloway	24/04/2020	1571	7	5	1	87	0
26155	Highland	04/05/2020	379	0	8	9	82	0
26154	South Ayrshire	11/05/2020	182	0	100	0	0	0
45967	Eilean Siar	10/02/2021	255	0	0	100	0	0
45968	Highland	10/02/2021	272	0	0	2	98	0
46319	Eilean Siar	11/02/2021	165	0	0	46	53	0
46320	Eilean Siar	11/02/2021	262	0	0	68	32	0
46321	Highland	13/02/2021	104	0	3	97	0	0
48591	Argyll and Bute	02/04/2021	132	0	2	10	88	0
48594	Argyll and Bute	08/04/2021	246	36	64	0	0	0
48839	Highland	15/04/2021	111	0	0	0	100	0
48775	Highland	16/04/2021	100	0	17	26	58	0
48866	Highland	21/04/2021	139	0	0	0	100	0
49673	Dumfries and Galloway	02/06/2021	253	0	55	44	1	0
192586	Highland	20/03/2022	221	0	0	0	100	0
199907	Eilean Siar	20/03/2022	448	0	0	83	17	0
199908	Eilean Siar	20/03/2022	220	0	0	0	100	0
200124	Highland	22/03/2022	395	0	8	1	91	0
200435	Highland	22/03/2022	116	0	100	0	0	0
199858	Highland	23/03/2022	330	22	41	23	13	0
199973	Highland	23/03/2022	198	0	0	36	64	0
200438	Highland	23/03/2022	134	0	20	8	73	0
199910	Eilean Siar	26/03/2022	1123	0	0	0	100	0
192587	Highland	27/03/2022	187	0	0	0	100	0
199855	Highland	28/03/2022	161	0	0	0	99	0
200723	Highland	28/03/2022	229	0	0	17	83	0
200241	Argyll and Bute	23/04/2022	204	0	90	9	1	0
201528	Highland	27/04/2022	584	0	3	0	97	0
215691	Perthshire and Kinross	10/03/2023	138	0	100	0	0	0
215722	Highland	08/04/2023	450	0	0	5	95	0
215724	Highland	08/04/2023	256	0	0	0	100	0
215745	Highland	19/04/2023	3448	1	27	19	54	0
216024	Highland	20/04/2023	106	0	0	0	99	0
216191	Highland	21/04/2023	114	0	1	5	95	0
216250	Stirling	22/04/2023	372	9	91	0	0	0
216217	Highland	05/05/2023	101	0	2	26	72	0
216417	Highland	29/05/2023	951	4	17	47	32	0
216596	Stirling	06/06/2023	283	0	100	0	0	0

D5-2 Climate Change Impacts on Natural Capital. Deliverable 2.5a: Estimate impacts on assets

Fire_ID	Local Authority	Fire Date	Area (ha)	VL (%)	L (%)	M (%)	H (%)	VH (%)
216597	Highland	10/06/2023	132	0	56	23	21	0
224477	Highland	28/01/2024	499	0	4	5	90	0
226639	Highland	09/03/2024	442	0	4	28	68	0
226679	Highland	10/03/2024	203	0	0	0	99	0
229482	Eilean Siar	01/04/2024	151	0	0	0	100	0
228778	Eilean Siar	02/04/2024	199	0	0	100	0	0
229804	Highland	24/04/2024	104	0	52	22	25	0
230017	Highland	04/05/2024	437	0	1	41	58	0
266008	Dumfries and Galloway	19/03/2025	103	0	1	0	99	0
265880	Highland	20/03/2025	199	0	0	1	99	0
267875	Highland	20/03/2025	313	0	14	3	83	0
265848	Highland	21/03/2025	108	61	39	0	0	0
265874	Highland	21/03/2025	374	0	0	1	99	0
265879	Highland	21/03/2025	498	0	1	0	99	0
265896	Highland	21/03/2025	117	32	68	0	0	0
267457	South Lanarkshire	01/04/2025	133	0	0	29	71	0
265898	Highland	02/04/2025	206	0	7	24	69	0
265707	Dumfries and Galloway	04/04/2025	6720	9	77	11	3	0
265729	Highland	05/04/2025	136	0	21	0	37	42
265761	Highland	06/04/2025	477	0	1	2	53	44
267478	Argyll and Bute	06/04/2025	617	0	80	15	6	0
267471	North Ayrshire	07/04/2025	157	0	30	70	0	0
267111	Highland	08/04/2025	291	0	2	34	63	0
267476	North Ayrshire	08/04/2025	889	3	17	0	80	0
267110	Eilean Siar	10/04/2025	254	0	0	0	100	0
267477	North Ayrshire	10/04/2025	528	2	35	23	40	0
267469	North Lanarkshire	11/04/2025	348	44	2	54	0	0
267480	Highland	11/04/2025	1080	0	8	1	90	1
269798	Highland	22/04/2025	393	31	69	0	0	0
273772	Highland	28/06/2025	9809	0	24	63	13	0

A3. Ignition Risk Class Maps

Fire ID: 613 - Date: 20/04/2020 – Area (ha): 253

Fire ID: 24398 - Date: 24/04/2020 – Area (ha): 1571

Fire ID: 24802 - Date: 20/04/2020 – Area (ha): 112

Fire ID: 26154 - Date: 11/05/2020 – Area (ha): 182

Fire ID: 26155 - Date: 04/05/2020 – Area (ha): 379

Fire ID: 45967 - Date: 10/02/2021 – Area (ha): 255

Fire ID: 45968 - Date: 10/02/2021 – Area (ha): 272

Fire ID: 46319 - Date: 11/02/2021 – Area (ha): 165

Fire ID: 46320 - Date: 11/02/2021 – Area (ha): 262

Fire ID: 46321 - Date: 13/02/2021 – Area (ha): 104

Fire ID: 48591 - Date: 02/04/2021 – Area (ha): 132

Fire ID: 48594 - Date: 08/04/2021 – Area (ha): 246

Fire ID: 48775 - Date: 16/04/2021 – Area (ha): 100

Fire ID: 48839 - Date: 15/04/2021 – Area (ha): 111

Fire ID: 48866 - Date: 21/04/2021 – Area (ha): 139

Fire ID: 49673 - Date: 02/06/2021 – Area (ha): 253

Fire ID: 192586 - Date: 20/03/2022 – Area (ha): 221

Fire ID: 192587 - Date: 27/03/2022 – Area (ha): 187

Fire ID: 199855 - Date: 28/03/2022 – Area (ha): 161

Fire ID: 199858 - Date: 23/03/2022 – Area (ha): 330

Fire ID: 199907 - Date: 20/03/2022 – Area (ha): 448

Fire ID: 199910 - Date: 26/03/2022 – Area (ha): 1123

Fire ID: 199973 - Date: 23/03/2022 – Area (ha): 198

Fire ID: 200124 - Date: 22/03/2022 – Area (ha): 395

Fire ID: 200241 - Date: 23/04/2022 – Area (ha): 204

Fire ID: 200435 - Date: 22/03/2022 – Area (ha): 116

Fire ID: 200438 - Date: 23/03/2022 – Area (ha): 134

Fire ID: 200723 - Date: 28/03/2022 – Area (ha): 229

Fire ID: 201528 - Date: 27/04/2022 – Area (ha): 584

Fire ID: 215691 - Date: 10/03/2023 – Area (ha): 138

Fire ID: 215722 - Date: 08/04/2023 – Area (ha): 450

Fire ID: 215724 - Date: 08/04/2023 – Area (ha): 256

Fire ID: 215745 - Date: 19/04/2023 – Area (ha): 3448

Fire ID: 216024 - Date: 20/04/2023 – Area (ha): 106

Fire ID: 216191 - Date: 21/04/2023 – Area (ha): 114

Fire ID: 216217 - Date: 05/05/2023 – Area (ha): 101

Fire ID: 216250 - Date: 22/04/2023 – Area (ha): 372

Fire ID: 216417 - Date: 29/05/2023 – Area (ha): 951

Fire ID: 216596 - Date: 06/06/2023 – Area (ha): 283

Fire ID: 216597 - Date: 10/06/2023 – Area (ha): 132

Fire ID: 224477 - Date: 28/01/2024 – Area (ha): 499

Fire ID: 226639 - Date: 09/03/2024 – Area (ha): 442

Fire ID: 226679 - Date: 10/03/2024 – Area (ha): 203

Fire ID: 228778 - Date: 02/04/2024 – Area (ha): 199

Fire ID: 229482 - Date: 01/04/2024 – Area (ha): 151

Fire ID: 229804 - Date: 24/04/2024 – Area (ha): 104

Fire ID: 230017 - Date: 04/05/2024 – Area (ha): 437

Fire ID: 265707 - Date: 04/04/2025 – Area (ha): 6720

Fire ID: 265729 - Date: 05/04/2025 – Area (ha): 136

Fire ID: 265761 - Date: 06/04/2025 – Area (ha): 477

Fire ID: 265848 - Date: 21/03/2025 – Area (ha): 108

Fire ID: 265874 - Date: 21/03/2025 – Area (ha): 374

Fire ID: 265879 - Date: 21/03/2025 – Area (ha): 498

Fire ID: 265880 - Date: 20/03/2025 – Area (ha): 199

Fire ID: 265896 - Date: 21/03/2025 – Area (ha): 117

Fire ID: 265898 - Date: 02/04/2025 – Area (ha): 206

Fire ID: 266008 - Date: 19/03/2025 – Area (ha): 103

Fire ID: 267110 - Date: 10/04/2025 – Area (ha): 254

Fire ID: 267111 - Date: 08/04/2025 – Area (ha): 291

Fire ID: 267457 - Date: 01/04/2025 – Area (ha): 133

Fire ID: 267469 - Date: 11/04/2025 – Area (ha): 348

Fire ID: 267471 - Date: 07/04/2025 – Area (ha): 157

Fire ID: 267476 - Date: 08/04/2025 – Area (ha): 889

Fire ID: 267477 - Date: 10/04/2025 – Area (ha): 528

Fire ID: 267478 - Date: 06/04/2025 – Area (ha): 617

Fire ID: 267480 - Date: 11/04/2025 – Area (ha): 1080

Fire ID: 267875 - Date: 20/03/2025 – Area (ha): 313

Fire ID: 269798 - Date: 22/04/2025 – Area (ha): 393

Fire ID: 273772 - Date: 28/06/2025 – Area (ha): 9809

